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Impact of Employment Equity Policies on staff retention. The case of the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa

By Pieter Cilliers van Ellewee

Student ID: H00065411

DISSERTATION ADVISOR: VEERESH SRIVASTAVA

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CERTIFICATION STATEMENT

I hereby certify that this paper constitutes my own product, that where the language of others is used, quotation marks so indicate, and that appropriate credit is given to the words, language, ideas, expressions, or writings of others, where used.

Pieter van Ellewee

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Abstract

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Executive Summary:

Employee equity has a strong impact on employee retention in business organisations. Gauteng, being among the economically wealthiest provinces of South Africa is one of the main retail hubs of the country. The retail industry in Gauteng is populated by both big retail giants as well as small-scale retail companies. The retail companies do not practice extreme disparity when it comes to treating employees holding lower positions in comparison to the top position employees. The lower-level employees are not even provided with decent compensations and safe accommodations. These abominable practices if not checked would gradually lead to employees employed in the retail sector moving to other industries which provide comparatively better facilities to employees. This means that the retail industry would face a shortage of employees in the future which would hamper its growth. Finally, it can be concluded that the retail companies operating in Gauteng should provide legitimate facilities to employees including proper salaries and accommodations to retain employees, thereby enjoying perpetual growth.

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Chapter 1. Introduction:

Chapter 1.1. Background:

Employment Equity Act, No 55 of 1998 was implemented in 1998 in South Africa “The purpose of this Act is to achieve equity in the workplace by-

(a) Promoting equal opportunity and fair treatment in employment through the elimination of unfair discrimination; and

(b) Implementing affirmative action measures to redress the disadvantages in employment experienced by designated groups, to ensure their equitable representation in all occupational categories and levels in the workforce.”

According to (Booyesen, 2007), South Africans have experienced great changes in the landscape of the employment relations in entities over the last two decades. Even though a huge number of legislations have been put in place in this country to achieve social justice, the overall progress made in redressing the unfair discrimination at the workplace has been uneven and quite slow. The findings of the authors identify various new barriers to retention and employment equity; these include the role of the white fear, as well as lack of the meaningful engagement of the white male employees.

The outcomes of this research study will underline the generalized overview of different issues in employment equity implementation and underline its impact on staff retention in the retail industry. Further, the findings can serve as useful pointers for effective implementation of the employment equity policy as well as effective retention of the staff in the organizations. It will be useful for the managers to understand how to implement employment equity successfully to facilitate the retention of staff in the organization. The findings will lead the management and managers to the new dimension with the holistic approach in the field of employment equity and employee retention. It will encourage them for reserving time for interacting with their subordinates.

This could help in building cohesive teams and creating trust among the staff, which ultimately enhances the job satisfaction of the staff, resulting in their retention in the workplace. Apart from this, the findings will be useful for the policymakers to understand whether to alter, change, or continue using the policy for its implementation in the

organizations. It may also be beneficial for the academicians to provide new insights to the students regarding the subject area. Moreover, the gaps found in this study will provide good scope to the practitioners and existing researchers for future research.

The real outcome of passing the Employment Equity Act was the opposite which necessitated passing the Employment Equity Amendment Bill in 2020. The bill aims to establish employment equity in different sectors in South Africa. Hlengiwe Octavia Mkhali, who is a prominent politician in the country mentions that the aim of the Employment Equity Act has been the establishment of employment equity in the different sectors in South Africa and abolishing workplace discrimination. The former governments have expected that the companies would voluntarily comply with the legislation and have not enforced any mandate to comply with the employment equity laws upon them. However, contrary to the expectation, the companies have not complied with the laws (SAnews.gov.za. 2020). This is evident from the fact that the employees employed with the retail outlets or spaza are the retail shops are called in South Africa are exploited even today. They are made to work for over 17 hours a day and seven days a week. They are underpaid with some of them earning as low as R 400 monthly. These exploited retail workers consisted of both domestic employees and foreign employees. The retail firms employing these retail workers are usually big retail firms that are financially strong. These upstream retail firms and logistics firms under whose payroll the spaza employees work have resorted to unethical practices like not entering into formal employment contracts and holding back their legitimate salary payments. These retail companies have held back the passports of the foreign employees illegally. Around 71% of the interviewed employees have reported that they have to sleep in the shop buildings or store fronts since they cannot afford proper accommodations owing to the low as well uncertain income (TheConversation.com. 2020). The retail sector in South Africa which includes both online retail companies and traditional retail companies is experiencing double-digit growth though it is smaller in comparison to its several foreign counterparts like the American retail sector (Businesswire.com. 2020). Thus, it can be construed that the retail sector in South Africa is growing in size which means it is employing an increasing number of people, thereby generating employment opportunities for the country. The retail sector in other words is emerging to be a significant driver of economic development and

generator of (Gross Domestic Product) GDP in South Africa. Thus, the sector has to be monitored by the stakeholders including the government to ensure that the players in the sector comply with employment equity legislations and do not exploit the workers, including the foreign workers.

Chapter 1.2. Relevance of the study:

Staff retention holds high importance for the growth of every sector including the retail sector. Gilani and Cunningham (2017) mention that employee retention has great significance in business organisations. They point out that on the one hand when employees resign from organisations, it has manifold negative impacts on the productivity of the organisations. Employees acquire, hold, and implement skills, experience as well as knowledge to carry out their professional duties. Thus, on the other hand, when employees resign and leave, the business organisations lose the knowledge, skills, and knowledge associated with the employees. Moreover, when an employee resigns, the workload which they used to bear has to be borne by the existing employees. This creates stress on them, thereby leading to absenteeism, more resignations, and ultimately poor business productivity at the concerned business organisations. As far as the retail sector in South Africa is concerned, the leading companies in the sector are exploiting the lower employees by using different means like underpaying them and not even providing them with safe accommodations (TheConversation.com. 2020). These inequalities in the treatment of employees in the retail sector in the country would gradually result in high employee turnover, thereby creating a shortage in the sector (Jang and Kandampully 2018). These two factors would combine to lead to lower productivity in the retail sector and then go on slow down the growth of the sector. The same fact holds for Gauteng, which is economically the wealthiest province of South Africa. The state has generated more than a third of the GDP of South Africa in 2017 (Statssa.gov.za 2021). The retail sector in the country owing to the presence of big players like Woolworths generates high revenue and contributes to the GDP of the country immensely (Farfan 2019). It can also be construed that Gauteng is one of the most important economic hubs of the country has a strong presence of retail companies which contribute to its GDP (Statssa.gov.za 2021). Thus, the prevailing employment inequality in the retail sector, if not checked would go on to hinder the growth of the economy of Gauteng and South Africa on the whole.

The relevance of the research lies in the fact that it aims to explore the impact employment inequality has on the employee retention of the retail industry of Gauteng. **The relevance of the study also lies in shedding light on the importance of checking employment inequality to ensure perpetual growth in an industry as well as the economy concerned. The industry considered is retail and the economy considered is Gauteng as well as South on the whole.**

Chapter 1.3. Methodology:

The research would adopt both primary and secondary data analysis. The research approach which would be used would be interpretivism.

Chapter 1.4. Research aim:

The research aim of this paper is to analyse the effect of employment equity on the retention of staff in companies in South Africa in the retail industry in Gauteng. The goal is to offer a description of different complex issues, contextual factors, multiple orientations, and forces impose upon employment equity implementation in respect of unfair discrimination between the staff, and retention of staff through the vehicle of investigation of South African companies in the retail sector in Gauteng.

Chapter 1.5. Research questions:

Hence, the questions of this research include the following:

- What is the state of fairness and discrimination of employment equity at the workplace in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa?
- What are the barriers to achieve equity in the employment policy in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa?
- What is the state of retention of staff in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa?
- What is the effect of employment equity on the retention of staff in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa?

Chapter 1.6. Research objectives:

The objectives of this research paper are as follows:

- To discuss employment equity in respect of fairness and discrimination at the workplace in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa.
- To analyze the barriers to achieving equity in the employment policy in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa.
- To explore the state of retention of staff in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa.
- To analyze the effect of employment equity on the retention of staff in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa.

Chapter 1.7. Feasibility of the study:

The secondary sources can be accessed easily from numerous resources available online, such as journal articles, books, and various others. In case of collecting data through the primary sources, interviews by approaching both employees and managers working in the retail companies in Gauteng, access will be possible by approaching various employees, ex-employees, and managers working in the retail industry in Gauteng to understand their views on the concern raised in this paper. A semi-structured interview will be used to extract the data.

The managers and employees will be approached for interviews with the help of using social media, especially LinkedIn, and snowballing to find the next participants. These sites can be used to approach the managers and employees. Hence, most likely these resources can be easily accessed. However, it will be ensured that all the information accessed online, or through interviews should be relevant to the study.

Chapter 1.5. Structure of the dissertation:

The dissertation would consist of five main chapters. The first chapter is the introductory chapter which would introduce the topic of discussion. The introductory would also lay the background of the research, its objectives, and the research questions. The second chapter in the literature review. The chapter would take into account the existing works on the topic and its related concepts like employee retention. The third chapter is the

research methodology which would delve into the approach adopted to conduct the research. The fourth chapter would analyse the data acquired. The fifth chapter would conclude the findings and recommend strategies for dealing with the issue based on the conclusion.

Chapter 2. Literature review:

Chapter 2.1. Employee retention:

During the past few decades, the retention of employees has become one of the perplexing and serious problems for all kinds of entities. Tirta and Enrika (2020) define the term employee retention as, **'an effort or way to encourage employees to remain in the organisation for a long period of time'**. Mwita and Tefurukwa (2018) define employee retention as **'is a process in which the employees are encouraged to remain with the organisation for the maximum period of time or until the completion of the project'**. Modau et al. (2018) on the other hand define employee turnover as, **'an organisation's inability to retain their employees'**. Mwita and Tefurukwa (2018) mention that employee retention is the inverse of employee turnover. Thus, in other words, business organisations should aim to retain their employees and minimise employee turnover. Arasanmi and Krishna (2019) mention that globalisation and increasing market competition necessitated companies to retain their employees. This is because the employees hold sets of skills, knowledge, and experience which constitute the knowledge capital of the companies concerned. The employees while performing their professional duties put these sets of experience, knowledge, and skills to use. This enables them to achieve higher performance and consequently attributes to the high performance of the companies concerned. Gilani and Cunningham (2017) mention that employer retention enables companies to develop and enhance their employer brand value in the market. They define the term employer branding as, **'The package of functional, economic and psychological benefits provided by employment, and identified with the employing company.'** They mention that enjoying strong employer branding enables companies to acquire more skilled employees. Nair and Bhattacharyya (2019) strengthen the argument by introducing a **resource-based view** or RBV. They mention that **'firms with assets that are valuable and rare possess a competitive advantage and have the potential to achieve superior financial performance'**. They continue that business organizations to sustain in the stringent market competition and improve their positions in the market should possess 'exclusive resources which are capable of providing them an edge over their competitors. It can be pointed out that firms can acquire more resources like financial resources and technological resources in the

long run even if they cannot acquire these resources in the near future. However, it can be pointed out that the organisations cannot acquire the knowledge capital of their competitors until and unless they can acquire their employees. Vrdoljak Raguž, Borovac Zekan and Peronja (2017) formulated that the knowledge capital which companies possess enables them to carry out innovations and create products to achieve higher competitive advantages in comparison to their competitors. Arasanmi and Krishna (2019) can be iterated to point out that the specific skills, experience, and knowledge which employees of companies possess enable them to serve customers in ways that differentiate them from their competitors. For example, the employees of companies using their skills and experience serve their customers more satisfactorily in comparison to their competitors. Thus, in other words, employees attribute competitive advantages to companies. Deducing, it can be construed from the analysis that the companies should retain their employees in order to retain their market positions (Hussinki et al. 2017). Thus, in other words in order to retain their knowledge capital, companies need to retain their employees. This is because when employees resign from companies and join their competitor companies, they carry their sets of sets of skills, talent, and knowledge. Hence, in other words, companies by losing their employees also lose their knowledge capital over their competitors. **It can be therefore pointed out that employee retention is a necessity.** It has also come to the forefront that companies to maintain their respective competitive advantages should not only retain talented employees but also acquire more talented employees. This means that companies to maintain their employer brand image and recruit more talented employees, need to retain their employees (Tumasjan et al. 2020). Thus, it can be pointed out based on this discussion that employee retention is an extremely important business objective companies need to achieve.

It has been reduced because of various factors, such as increasing dissatisfaction among the employees relating to the job and unfair discrimination at the workplace. The findings by the researchers (Harris, Lavelle, and McMahan 2020) supports the significance of favouritism by indicating that turnover intentions of the non-beneficiaries are higher in the family entities when they perceive high favouritism; favouritism in the family entities positively influences the violation of a psychological contract; psychological contract violation acts as the mediator of the association between favouritism and

turnover intention of non-beneficiaries; and climate of job insecurity and authentic leadership act as the moderators of the relationship between favouritism and intention of turnover. Davies and Ollus (2019) mention that labour exploitation in different sectors has increased in the 2000s. The management of the companies to gain profits or any other business objective, often resort to exploitation of their respective employees. They commit actions that are unethical and illegal. These actions tend to harm the safety and well-being of the employees. Labour exploitation is a corporate crime but management and senior-level managers often resort to it for their own gains. Masayuki (2017) mentions that unjustified disparity between the remunerations of the upper-level employees and the lower-level employees is a common form of exploitation of the lower-level employees. Weil (2018) point out that management of companies should pay their employee legitimately. Underpayment of employees or withholding their legitimate salary is unethical and illegal. Pang and Lu (2018) mention in this respect that legitimate salary has positive impacts on the motivation of employees. When employees receive a legitimate salary, they feel more motivated to continue working with the employers concerned. Chan et al. (2017) on the other hand mention that when remuneration is one of the factors which result in turnover intentions among employees which in turn goes to increases the probability of employee turnover. This means that when the employees are not paid legitimately or there exist unjustifiable disparities between the employees of higher designations and the lower designations, the employees are dissatisfied. They feel the intentions to resign since they are underpaid. Kurniawaty, Ramly, and Ramlawati (2019) mention that employees working environment has a strong role to play in upholding employment equity and retaining employees. When the quality of the working environment in which employees of higher designations work and the environment in which employees holding lower designations work differs a lot, there arise turnover intentions among the lower designation employees. For example, the individual members of the board of directors of a company sit in comfortable cabins and the employees holding lower positions have to sit in an open office space that is too noisy and stuffy to work properly in. The lower-level employees, in that case, are likely to feel frustrated, lack of motivation, and be stressed. They are more likely to feel turnover intentions. Thus, it can be pointed out that lack of employment equity-like underpayment of workers and not

providing them with an appropriate working environment would likely result in employee turnover.

As far as the retail sector in South Africa is concerned, there exist wide disparities between the treatments meted out to the lower-level employees in comparison to their upper-level counterparts. They are often made to work for long hours without any weekly off. They are underpaid and even the meagre salaries they earn are often withheld. They are made to sleep out either in the open and in the shop front (TheConversation.com. 2020). There has been widespread political unrest in the country which has led to the killing of people, looting of retail shops, and explosions taking place in the ATMs. The provinces hit by the unrest include Gauteng as well (Aljazeera.com. 2021). This means that by sleeping in the shop front, the lower-level retail employees are risking their own lives. Thus, it can be pointed out in this case that the level of inequality existing in the retail industry in South Africa is inhuman. It can be pointed out that the employees employed with the retail companies owing to this inhuman level of exploitation would gradually seek employment in other industries in the country like banking. The banking industry in the country is booming and becoming increasingly competitive (Pwc.co.za. 2021). The retail sector would consequently face a shortage of employees which would go on to inhibit its smooth operations and gradually go on to impair its growth in the long run. Thus, it can be established based on this analysis that failure to curb employee exploitation and retain employees would impair the future growth of the retail sector in South Africa.

Chapter 2.2. Role of leadership in employment equity and employee retention:

Leadership plays a very significant role in employment equity and employee retention.

Hauer, Quan, and Liang (2021) define the term leadership as, '**a social influencing process aiming to achieve voluntary dedication and effort of subordinates**'. They

mention leadership as, '**a comparatively persistent behavioural pattern, which characterizes and describes a leader**'. Yanto and Aulia (2021) supporting the previous

authors mention, '**leadership involves a process of influence. Leaders in practice always have at least one follower because, without this, one cannot become a**

leader.' This means that leadership has several attributes which come to play in organisational management. Leaders can influence their subordinate employees to motivate them to strive to achieve certain predetermined targets. It has also come to the light that leaders cannot carry out their functions without the power to influence the employees. It appears that leadership is mainly crystallised around influencing employees to make effort and achieve certain predetermined targets. Sugiarta, Yuesti, and Sudja (2021) on the other hand mention, '**Organizational leaders must be able to use their authority to change employee attitudes and behaviour so they can work actively and want to achieve optimal results, leadership styles are used by leaders to be able to influence employee performance through thoughts, feelings,**' This means that responsibilities of the leaders go way beyond merely influencing the subordinates to achieve set goals. The leaders should be able to influence the subordinates and bring about positive changes among them. The employees should not be coerced to achieve their targets. They should be rather be motivated to achieve the targets by the leaders. Leaders can bring about these positive changes by understanding the feelings and thoughts of the subordinate rather than merely ordering them. The leaders should encourage employees to continuously improve their performances. Ridlwan, Purwandari, and Syah (2021) on the other hand mention that to ensure that the business operations can continue smoothly, leaders should collaborate with the workers to achieve the targets rather than merely instructing them around. Susanto and Sigit, (2021) mention that organisational leaders are responsible for the establishment of a strong organisational culture within the business organisations concerned. Borowiecki et al. (2021) point out that organisational leaders are also responsible for making decisions regarding the

operations of the organisations they lead. Several facts have come into the light regarding the role of leadership in ensuring a high level of organisational performance. Leaders play a tremendously important role by influencing the subordinates to work towards the achievement of certain predetermined goals. However, its operation of influencing is not composed of mere instructions. The leaders have to make decisions and make strategies to achieve the goals. The subordinate employees would be responsible for implementing these strategies. The leaders should push the employees to improve their performances. This aspect of leadership is linked to employee engagement, training, and mentoring. Moss (2021) in this respect mentions that organisational leaders should engage the employees in organisational operations. The employees consequently would feel passionate about achieving the targets rather than achieving the targets because they have been assigned to them. The organisational leaders should provide training and mentoring to the employees, thereby enabling them to improve their performance. The employees would consequently proactively collaborate with the managers leading them to take instructions from them and implement the instructions. They may also pose questions and have them answered to gain a better understanding of the strategies. This means that collaborating with the subordinate employees enables the leaders to lead the former towards the achievement of the goals. It has also come to the light that the organisational leaders are responsible for making decisions regarding operations. One of the key areas of organisational operations which requires meticulous decision making is human resource management of which employee retention forms an important component. Park, Kim, and Nguyen (2021) mentions that organisational leaders should make decisions on retaining employees rather than only using them to achieve

organisational targets. Arasanmi and Krishna (2019) can be iterated that employees using their special sets of knowledge, skills, and experiences perform the job responsibilities including executing the strategies to achieve the targets. Thus, in other words, it can be pointed out that the organisational leaders including both the top-level managers and the departmental heads cannot achieve the business targets or any organisational target in that matter without the support of their teams of subordinate employees. Hauer, Quan, and Liang (2021) in this respect that employee retention is one of the main challenges which companies are facing today. They mention that business organisations to be able to perform strongly and hold onto their market positions need to retain their employees. However, the increasing rate of employee turnover is one of the main weaknesses which is affecting most business organisations. Rising employee turnover is one of the main issues concerning the management of business organisations. Thus, it can be deduced that employee retention is an important aspect of corporate leadership. This means that the management of the companies should adopt strategies to retain employees to retain their market leadership. Employment equity is the most important component of employee retention. The management bodies of the business organisations should treat its employee inclusively. This means that they should be provided with facilities as per their entitlements and there should not occur unjustified disparities in their treatments. For example, employees from different cultural backgrounds, religious identities, marital status, sexual orientations should be treated with equal dignity and acceptance. Female employees and differently-abled employees should be treated with respect. The other employees should not behave in ways that could hurt their sentiments and make them feel uncomfortable (Brown 2018). The management of the business organisations has to

play a very significant role in the establishment of employment equity. Cassell et al. (2021) in this respect point out that employee inclusion policies should be included in the HR policies and strategies. This means that if any employee who ill-treats his/her co-workers on the grounds of diversity like disrespecting an employee on the ground of cultural differences would be violating the HR policies. The employee if proven to have violated HR policies would be liable for actions as per management decisions. Thus, in this respect, it could be expected that such employees would be likely to treat each other respectfully. The Bell (2021) points out a very important aspect of employment equity which is employee compensation. He mentions that business organisations should compensate their employee legitimately which means that the employees should be compensated as per their contribution towards the organisation's performance. For example, the employees holding positions on the management board receive high salaries. The employees holding the lowest rung in the organisational hierarchy should be paid legitimate salaries. Their salaries should at least be capable of meeting the needs. The employees who perform target-based jobs should be provided with legitimate incentives (Weerasinghe and Yashodha 2018). Similarly, the employees both holding higher positions and lower positions in the business organisations expect to enjoy work-life balance (Joecks 2021). They should be provided with leaves so that they could meet their personal duties (Lagrana. and Bayoneta 2021). The employees irrespective of designations should be provided with paid sick leaves so that they can take care of themselves when they fall sick. The employees should be allowed to take fixed numbers of leaves to spend time with their respective families and go on vacations. Bültmann and Christensen (2021) contradict this view and point out that unabated employment equity

benefits do not have any positive impacts on employee retention. This is because employees tend to misuse these benefits at the expense of the company's interests. They mention that certain employees to enjoy long holidays misuse their sickness certificates. They exhibit that they are sick and their rest periods need to be extended. This means that the employees remain absent for long periods of time. It can be pointed out that if several employees remain absent by furnishing medical certificates wrongly, the companies concerned would not be able to make sufficient numbers of employees on board to carry out their daily operations. They would not be able to serve their customers satisfactorily owing to a shortage of staff members (Samosir, Rachbini, and Rekarti 2021). This means that the companies concerned would end up receiving customer escalations and losing a percentage of their customers to their competitors. This also means that the market position of these companies would gradually weaken. Thus, it can be construed from the discussion that employment equity undoubtedly enhances employee retention rates in business organisations. However, unabated and loosely supervised employee facilities utilisation can result in misuse of these facilities by certain sections of the employees at the expense of the interests of the company. Thus, it can be construed that the management bodies of the companies should ensure that the employment equity facilities allowed to the employees are not misused by sections of employees so that all the employees can use them legitimately, or else the facilities would have to be withdrawn. It can be pointed out that the management of the companies should incorporate these employment equity policies on the employment contracts and employee management policies. For example, the managers should be able to enjoy more casual leaves in comparison to lower-level employees. Similarly, the employees holding profiles

that require achievements of certain business targets should be allowed paid leaves to go on trips that may be sponsored by the companies. It can also be pointed out that this system of providing employees holding positions with more facilities in comparison with the employees holding lower positions has certain positive effects on the employees as well as their performances. These employees holding lower positions often want to be promoted to higher positions to enjoy the facilities and perks associated with those higher positions (Howell 2017). Thus, they put in more effort in performing and proving themselves worthy of promotions to higher positions. They consequently end up performing better which ultimately pushes the performances of the companies on the whole up. Thus, it can be established that the extra facilities which employees holding higher designations get to motivate the lower-level employees to work harder (Kumari 2021). The employees of the companies view these extra facilities to which managers are entitled as signs of recognition of the huge responsibilities which the high-level employees take. Thus, facilities that high-level employees enjoy to some extent have positive impacts on the employees in general.

It has come to the light that leadership has several profound effects on employment equity and employee retention in business organisations. It has also come to the light that the management bodies of the business organisations play a very important role in establishing employment equity and employee retention (Weerasinghe and Yashodha 2018). Howell (2017) mentions on the other hand that though perks that higher-level managers receive may motivate the employees to work harder to be promoted to higher positions to enjoy these perks, they do not necessarily promote employee engagement. Barik and Kochar (2017) point out that employees besides being instructed, want to feel

that the management is concerned about them. This encourages them to get more engaged in the operations. They feel more committed and in general deliver higher levels of performance. They mention that leadership plays a very important role in managing and monitoring the employees to ensure that they operate in the desired manner to attain the expected performance. They point out in this respect that there are several styles of leadership like autocratic style, democratic style, and transformational style which leaders can adopt in different situations. Rao and Zaidi (2020) in this respect mention that most of the management bodies prefer using autocratic leadership. This is because they feel that it is important to control the activities of the employees to ensure that they perform well and achieve the expected targets. They however mention that it has also been identified that autocratic leadership does not contribute to the organisational performances significantly since it does not result in employee engagement. Krawczyk-Sołtys (2017) mentions that effective leaders are the ones who know to adapt the leadership style as per the situations. They can relate to their followers and inspire them to bring about improvements in their performances continuously. Effective apex leaders can gain the loyalty of the subordinate employees for the business organisations they lead. Wang (2017) mentions that in the case of autocratic leadership, leaders use power asymmetry to exercise authority over their subordinates. The leaders, in this case, have been known to have resorted to manipulation and coercion to have the targets achieved by the subordinates without having any concern about the impact of these unethical activities on the latter. Houghton et al. (2021) support this view mentioning that the autocratic leadership style, as a result, is often associated with employee bullying. This is because autocratic managers feel satisfied by coercing and bullying their employees.

They even go to the extent of punishing employees even when not required to feel their power and authority over their subordinate employees. Allafchi (2017) points out that democratic leadership on the other hand enforces a high level of collaboration. This is because leaders following the democratic style communicate a lot, unlike their autocratic peers. Fiaz, Su, and Saqib (2017) supporting the view of the previous author point out that democratic leaders are essentially concerned about their teams and the members belonging to the team. The leaders following a democratic leadership style usually encourage their subordinates to participate in the process of decision-making. They assume that the subordinates are self-motivated and responsible. They also presume that their subordinates would love to take challenges. However, in reality, all employees may not be equally responsible and self-motivated. Some employees may be cynical and may establish a negative attitude towards the decisions of the management no matter what. However, it has been observed that democratic leadership can even motivate cynical employees to perform (Ince 2018). However, the fact may not hold in all situations. Margelytė-Pleskienė and Vveinhardt (2018) point out that cynical employees do resist organisational changes especially when they feel less involved or not involved in the process. Some of the cynical employees may not cooperate even when involved in the operations. Thus, in other words, democratic leadership may not hold appropriate for them. Thus, in this case, they have to be warned to keep their cynical attitude under control and have to be monitored closely by the managers (Wang, 2017). Thus, in other words, the autocratic leadership style holds appropriate in situations when employees have to be reprimanded and controlled for their unprofessional behavior. Shafi et al. (2020) bring into the discussion a third leadership style which is the transformational

leadership style. They mention that the transformational leadership style has gained much attention in terms of corporate leadership. A comparison between democratic leadership and transformational leadership shows that the latter draws strength from the former. Transformational leadership like democratic leadership emphasises employee participation. However, instead of presuming that employees are trained as in the case of democratic leadership style, transformational leadership style takes into account that employees have to be competent to handle responsibilities. Transformational leaders train their subordinates. They encourage them to innovative and creative. Yin et I. (2019) support the opinion of the previous authors by mentioning that transformational leaders focus on share of knowledge among their subordinates. This means that the senior, more experienced, and more knowledgeable members of their teams are encouraged to mentor the junior employees usually having less knowledge and less experience. Thus, it can be construed that transformational leadership style enables employee engagement through the process of employee collaboration, thereby motivating the employees, traits it shares with democratic leadership style. Further, the result of the study by authors (Sahu, Pathardikar, and Kumar 2018) reveals that the transformational style of leadership directly influences the retention of the employee to leave. Transformational leadership and employer branding are mediated by employee engagement. The relationship of leadership with psychological attachment is mediated by employer branding. Similarly, the research findings by the researchers (Kundu and Lata 2017) suggest that a supportive work environment plays a crucial role in predicting the retention of an employee. The organizational engagement partially mediates the relationship between the supportive work environment and retention of an employee.

The result of the study by authors (Michael, Prince, and Chacko 2016) found that there exists a significant relationship between the satisfaction of job and retention of an employee, the more any employee is satisfied, there would be more chances of them to remain in the organization for a longer period. Bason (2019) mentions that employee retention is a 'major concern' for business organisations. This is because employees can directly influence the business productivity, efficiency, and sustainability of the organisations concerned. This is because the employees are the ones who execute the strategies formed by the higher management. They interact with the customers and serve them, thereby generating revenue for the organisations they work for. The employees are the resources who mobilise all the other resources of the organisations including knowledge, technology, and machinery to serve customers. Thus, to ensure they keep on reaping the benefits like high market position and sustainability in the face of the growing market competition, the management bodies of the companies have to focus on retaining their employees. Sheraz, Batool, and Adnan (2019) mention that employee job satisfaction is closely related to employee retention. This is because when employees experience job satisfaction upon working with companies they are employed with, they are more likely to continue working with the companies for a longer period. The opportunities of obtaining professional development play a very important role in employees experiencing job satisfaction. Ocen, Francis, and Angundaru (2017) mention that professional development opportunities like training have positive impacts on employee job satisfaction. The authors mention that the continuously evolving global economy today necessitates business organisations to train their employees with new skills and knowledge, which ultimately adds to their respective knowledge capital. The

employees having been trained, can perform better. Performing better increases their chances of being promoted to higher positions. The employees owing to their new skills and knowledge can also apply for more high-paying jobs in other organisations. They are in short obtain career development opportunities in the organisations they are employed with and in other organisations. This means that are less likely to be laid off or are least more likely to be employed again even if laid off. That is why employees view training and career development opportunities as important to experience job satisfaction.

Figure 1. Figure showing relationship between employee job satisfaction, employee retention, and career development programs

(Source: Sheraz, Batool and Adnan 2019)

Similarly, the research by (Hideg and Ferris 2014) examined the practices of human resources that promote retention of an employee. The outcomes of their study showed that there is a significant impact of HR practices on employee retention. Comparatively, the findings by researchers (Coetzee and Stoltz 2015) suggest that the career concerns, plans, and goals of employees and the way these relate to the practices of retention are significant for retaining them.

Chapter 2.3. Impact of employment equity on staff retention:

Employee equity has strong positive influences on staff retention. Iqbal, Guohao. and Akhtar (2017) mention several components which form employment equity and go on to influence employee retention. **The components are employee compensation, organisational culture, power distance index, uncertainty avoidance index, and long term orientation vs short term orientation.** How management boards leading different organisations to deal with them go a long way in the establishment of employment equity and retain employees. Chan et al. (2017) can be iterated to point out the employee compensations and level of parity in it is one of the main aspects of employment equity. When there exists a justified disparity between the compensations of the upper-level employees and the lower-level employees, there exists a low level of employment equity in the organisations concerned. The employees in such organisations are more likely to feel the low motivation to continue working with them. Similarly, business organisations having high power indices are less likely to retain employees. This is because owing to the high power index, there exist huge differences between the compensations and benefits enjoyed by the employees holding high levels in comparison to employees holding lower levels. This means that employees holding higher positions are more likely to coerce and exploit the lower rung employees, in other words, lead them autocratically (Wang 2017). This means the lower rung employees are less likely to experience job satisfaction and feel the urge to leave the organisations concerned (Lin et al. 2019). Business organisations having a higher level of uncertainty avoidance are more likely to retain employees (De Silva 2017). This is because employees employed with these organisations are more prepared to face uncertain situations which can be inferred that they are trained to face risks and uncertain situations (Ocen, Francis, and Angundaru 2017). They are more likely to perform and experience higher job satisfaction. They are more likely to serve the business organisations for a longer span of time. Thus, in other words. A long-term orientation attitude in business organisations encourages employee retention and employee job satisfaction (Iqbal, Guohao. and Akhtar 2017). When The research by the authors (Konrad, Yang, and Maurer, 2016) found that the diversity and equality management practices need to be considered as the bundles and that the vertical relation to the strategy is significant for the effectiveness of diversity and equality

management practices. On the other hand, the authors (Haider *et al.* 2015) found in their study that threat of self-image influences reactions to the gender-based Employment Equity policies. Research by (Vasquez 2014) revealed that the creation of a good environment of working including the support of management, incentive programs, and rewards would result in the retention of an employee. Similarly, the researchers (Maphisa, Zwane, and Yide 2017) sought the perception of management of succession planning and its impact on the retention at the sugar manufacturing entity. It was found by the authors that the entity is not doing enough for implementing programmes of succession even though there include potential candidates who can be developed and trained into managerial positions. On the other hand, the author (Anitha 2016) revealed in the research paper that the culture of organization is having a high impact on the retention of employees compared to normative commitment and continuing commitment, which implies employees have more positive perceptions regarding the culture of an organization.

Research paper by (Long and Perumal 2014), found in their research study that performance management at the workplace appears to have the strongest impact on the intention of employee turnover. The HRM practices of an organization have a great impact on the employees' turnover intention. Further, a research paper by (Divincová and Siváková 2014) has found that the issue of mobbing at the workplace significantly affects the employees' performance, which ultimately results in employees leaving the company. A research paper by (Khoele and Daya 2014) stated that in South Africa, turnover, employment, and retention occurs against the backdrop of the history of inequality and discrimination and the organizations and government's attempts at redress. The researchers have revealed that the increased turnover of employees has an adverse impact on the profitability and productivity of the organization.

Hence, so far, there is no study on employment equity in respect of fairness and discrimination at the workplace in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa. Further, the study has also not been done on the effect of employment equity on the retention of staff in the retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa. This gap, therefore, provided the scope to

conduct the research on the effect of employment equity on retention of staff in the companies in South Africa in the retail industry in Gauteng.

Chapter 2.4. Barriers to the achievement of equity in employment policy:

There are several barriers to the establishment of employment equity that business organisations face. One of the most important factors which inhibit the establishment of employee equity is the lack of appropriate leadership. Houghton et al. (2021) can be iterated to point out that autocratic leadership is commonly responsible for inhibiting the establishment of employment equity. Autocratic leaders, in general, perceive that they need to monitor and control their leaders to push them to achieve certain targets. Autocratic leaders assume that the employees are incapable of taking decisions and have to be pushed to perform. The autocratic leaders in comparison to democratic leaders are often less concerned about their employees and are only concerned about the attainment of the goals. (Fiaz, Su, and Saqib 2017). They often resort to bullying and ill-treating employees to achieve targets. Salin and Hoel (2020) mention in this respect that employee bullying results in creating stress among the employees. They owing to the support of the managers do not have a clear idea or knowledge about the strategies. They consequently are not executed properly. They feel insecure about the consequences of poor performance. Thus, it can be established that lack of appropriate leadership and prevalence of autocratic leadership style is largely responsible for lack of employment equity in the organisations concerned. For example, the management of the retail companies in South Africa practices an authoritative leadership style. They do not show concern for their employees. The employees are made to work for long hours and not given any week offs. They are not even paid legitimate salaries and whatever little is paid is often held back. The employees are not even provided proper accommodations and are often made to sleep outside the retail outlets. The meagre salaries they receive cannot afford them proper accommodations (TheConversation 2020). Thus, it can be established that the lack of leadership is responsible for the poor establishment of employee equity in organisations. The second factor responsible for the lack of employment equity is poor organisational culture. Susanto and Sigit, (2021) mention that a strong organisational culture means that the employees of different designations are treated with respect. The

employees irrespective of designations are involved in the process of decision making and proper with proper professional development opportunities including training. Ocen, Francis, and Angundaru (2017) can be reiterated to point out that training enables the employees to gain new sets of knowledge and skills. They are consequently able to implement the newly derived knowledge and skills to improve their performances to gain promotions to higher positions and the perks which come with them. This means that in the absence of a strong organisational culture, the employees, especially the lower level cannot avail of professional development opportunities. Thus, they cannot avail promotions to higher positions and the benefits associated with the promotions like increase in salaries. Thus, the gap between the compensations received by the employees holding higher positions and the ones holding lower positions keeps on widening. Thus, it can be established that the lack of a strong organisational culture is responsible for a low level of employment equity in business organisations. The third factor which can be held responsible for the lack of employment equity in business organisations is the lack of external stakeholder intervention. Employer brand image is one of the most important intangible assets of business organisations (Tumasjan et al. 2020). When there is a lack of intervention of external stakeholders like the society and media in the operations of business organisations, they do not fear the loss of their employer brand images. They consequently indulge in unethical activities like exploiting employees, thereby resulting in low employment equity.

Chapter 3. Research methodology:

Chapter 3.1. Introduction:

Methodology in research is referred to as the systematic method for resolving a research problem by gathering data using different techniques and tools, providing an interpretation of the gathered data, and lastly, drawing conclusions regarding the data that has been researched (Babatunde and Low 2015). In this paper, the grounded theory approach will be used for collecting and analyzing the data. The research approaches to be used in this paper will be pure interpretivism, and qualitative. The interpretivism research approach is referred to as the theories regarding the way knowledge of the world can be gained that loosely rely upon the understanding or interpretation of the meanings attached by humans to their actions (Cresswell 2014). This approach claims that study of the human society should go beyond the supposedly and empirical objective evidence to include subjective opinions, views, values, and emotions, which implies the things that cannot be observed and counted directly (Gupta and Awasthy 2015). On the other hand, qualitative research includes collecting and analysing non-numerical data for understanding opinions, concepts, or experiences. It is a multi-method focusing on the naturalistic and interpretive approach to its subject matter. This approach will be used for finding the trends in the opinions and thoughts and dive good insights regarding the effect of Employment equity on staff retention in the South African companies (Mukhopadhyay and Gupta 2014).

Chapter 3.2. Data collection methods:

The data to be used in this paper will be mixed, which are both secondary data sources and primary data sources. This paper will use various scholarly publications, books, newspapers, magazines, various reports published by the South African retail companies, and other sources relating to the concern of the effect that Employment Equity has on the retention of staff in South African entities in the retail sector. Moreover, in the case of primary sources, on a random basis, around 20 managers and employees (10 managers and 10 employees) working in the retail companies in Gauteng, South Africa, will be interviewed virtually or by telephone regarding the effect of employment equity on staff retention in South African entities. Access to interviews will be possible by approaching various employees, ex-employees, and managers working in

the retail industry in Gauteng to understand their views on the concern raised in this paper. A semi-structured interview will be used to extract the data. The managers and employees will be approached with the help of using social media, especially LinkedIn, and snowballing to find further participants. These sites can be used to approach the managers and employees. The interview will be conducted by asking different questions from the participants, related to the concern of the impact of employment equity on staff retention. It will be ensured that their consent is taken before going for an interview (Glesne 2016). The data processing technique to be used in a research paper will be IPA theory. An Interpretative phenomenological analysis is a qualitative approach that aims to provide a detailed examination of the personal lived experience.

Further, the concepts of validity and reliability will be used to evaluate the quality of the research. They show how well a technique, test or method, measures something. It will be ensured that the consistency of measures used in this research is reliable, and the accuracy of measures used is maintained. In the research paper, 1-2 pilot interviews will be conducted for testing the interview questions. The main purpose of doing a pilot study is to find out the existence of any flaws in the interview plans and questions. Interviews are the measuring instrument employed in this research study. The applicability and responsiveness of this tool will be ensured with the help of the pilot study by checking the reliability and validity of the interviews. Further, member checking is also important, which can be done by going back to the interviewees after transcription for making sure that their meanings and views are properly captured and are correctly interpreted. Apart from this, another colleague will be asked to do the coding of themes, for seeing if there is much divergence. Coding is the significant means through which one can find meaning to the data. Excellence in coding leads to excellence in the outcomes of research. It will be ensured that rich and descriptive data, including verbatim quotes from the interviews, will be used for ensuring reliability and validity. In addition, triangulation with management and staff; identification of the researcher bias, and presentation of discrepant and negative data can also help. The application of these strategies will help in ensuring validity and reliability in the qualitative study. Further, comparison and contrast of different entities and better coverage by different interviewees will help in boosting the validity and reliability.

Chapter 3.3. Ethical considerations:

This research paper will follow the ethical guidelines within conducting the research. The privacy and confidentiality of the participants will be respected. Further, there will be the use of verifiable and honest methods in performing, proposing, and evaluating the research. The results of the research will be reported with particular attention to the adherence to regulations, rules, guidelines, regulations, and following the accepted professional norms and codes (Dooly, Moore, And Vallejo 2017)

Chapter 4. Data analysis and results

Chapter 4.1 Introduction

It is one of the most important chapters in the research paper. This paper helps in presenting the analysis of the results which further helps in concluding the results of the result. It is very much important for the scholar to analyse the research very much correctly to get accurate results. For the research, the scholar has surveyed the employees which have helped in better understanding of the topic.

Chapter 4.2 Presentation and discussion of the quantitative data (survey)

1. What is your gender?

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
female	46 %	11	24
male	54 %	13	24

Table 1: Age group

This is the random question being asked to comprehend the factors of demographics. Here the factor of age is being comprehended. Among the 24 respondents who took part in the survey, 11 of the candidates were female which is about 46 percent is and on the other hand, 13 male candidates took part in the survey which is 54 percent.

2. What is your age?

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Under 25 years	0 %	0	24
25- 30 years	13 %	3	24
31-40 years	33%	8	24
41-50 years	50%	12	24
Above 50 years	4%	1	24

Table 2: Age group

This question mainly represents the age group of the candidates who participated in the survey. Among the 24 candidates who took part in the survey, it is being found that 0

candidates belonged under the age group of 25 years, 3 candidates belonged to the age group of 25- 30 years which presents the 13 percent of the candidates, 8 candidates which are 33 percent of the candidates falls under the age group of 31-40 years, 12 candidates fall under the category of 41-50 years which is around 50 percent of the total candidates and 1 candidate belonged to the category of the age group above 50 years.

3. Please indicate your relevant highest education attainment levels to date. Please tick the most appropriate below

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Below standard 8 (grade 10) or equivalent	4%	1	24
Standard 9 (Grade 11) or equivalent	0%	0	24
Standard 10 (matric or grade 12) or equivalent	25%	6	24
Post matric	8%	2	24
diploma	29%	7	24
Undergraduate degree- bachelor's degree	3%	3	24
Postgraduate degree- honours degree	3%	3	24
Postgraduate masters	4%	1	24
Postgraduate degree- doctorate	0%	0	24
Other (please specify)	4%	1	24

Table 3: Age group

This question presents the qualification of the candidates who took part in the survey. 4 percent of the candidates belong to the category which is below standard 8, 0 percent of the candidates belonged to the category of standard 9, 25 percent of the candidates

belonged to the standard 10 categories of qualification, 8 percent of the candidates belonged to the post-matric, 3 percent of the candidates belonged to the undergraduate degree- bachelor's degree, 3 percent of the candidates belonged to the postgraduate degree honours degree, 4 percent of the candidates belonged to the postgraduate masters, 0 percent of the candidates belonged to the postgraduate degree doctorate and lastly, 4 percent of the candidates belonged to the category of others.

4. What is your current employee status?

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
unemployed	0%	0	24
Employed- full time	83%	19	24
Employed- part-time	9%	2	24
Employed- a contract worker	9%	2	24
Employed- temporary	0%	0	24

Table 4: Employment status

This table presents the status of the employment of the candidates who participated in the survey. The table presents that 0 percent of the candidates were unemployed, 83 percent of the candidates were involved in full-time employment, 9 percent of the candidates were in part-time employment, 9 percent of the candidates were contract workers and none of the employees were employed temporarily.

5. Gender discrimination - please tick appropriately to the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following

Options	Strongly disagree (participant)	disagree 5	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Standard deviation	Responses
I have been harassed at least once in my workplace	42 % (10)	17% (4)	8 % (2)	17% (4)	17% (4)	2.71	24
Have been discriminated against based on my gender in my workplace	38 %(9)	17% (4)	4 %(1)	25%(6)	17 %(4)	2.64	24
My direct manager/supervisor is gender-neutral in allocating tasks	13 %(3)	4% (1)	21 %(5)	29 % (7)	33% (8)	2.56	24
Have faced adverse treatment on my gender	38 %(9)	21%(5)	21% (5)	13% (3)	8 %(2)	2.4	24
Have previously been discriminated against on pregnancy grounds in the retail industry	52 %(12)	9 %(2)	35 %(8)	4% (1)	0 (0)	4.63	24

Table 5: Gender discrimination

From the above survey, the prevalence of gender discrimination in the workplace is evident. 17 percent of the candidates claim that they have been harassed in the workplace once. The standard deviation is 2.71. since the value here is above 1, there is a higher level of risk in this question. The fact that the harassment is faced by the employees in the workplace is presented through the question.

In the second question, though 38 percent of the candidates disagree with the fact that they are being discriminated against based on gender, 17 percent of the candidates agree to it. The standard deviation is 2.64. This indicates that there is risk and therefore the management of the organizations must prevent such discriminations

In the third question, 33 percent of the candidates claim that the manager is neutral in allocating the task. However, 13 percent of the candidates disagree with it. The value of the standard deviation is 2.64. There is risk associated with how the manager allocates the task and therefore some different ways of allocating the task must be taken into the consideration.

38 percent of the candidates claim that they did not face any adverse treatment based on gender. However, 13 and 8 percent of the candidates agree and strongly agree with. The value of the standard deviation is 2.56. Therefore, the management must take initiatives in looking into the matter so that no adverse treatment takes place among the employees.

52 percent of the candidates strongly disagree that previously, they have been discriminated in the basis of the pregnancy. The std value is 4.63. the company must look into the matter and ensure no such discrimination occurs.

6. In your current workplace or a previous workplace in the retail industry with Gauteng, South Africa, have you been discriminated against on the grounds of your race. Please tick appropriately. Have been discriminated against for being:

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
African	14%	3	23
Indian	5%	1	23
Coloured	0%	0	23
Caucasian	76%	16	23
Other (please specify)	14%	3	23

Table 6: Discrimination based on race

The table represents the fact that 76 percent of the Caucasian candidates faced discrimination. 5 percent of the Indians faced discrimination, 14 percent of the Africans faced discrimination and the other candidates belonging to other races even faced discrimination. Therefore, race can be considered as the significant factor considering which discrimination takes place.

7. Disability discrimination – do you have any physical disability

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Yes	4	1	24
no	96	23	24

Table 7: Physical disability rate

The table presents that only 4 percent of the candidates have disability issues whereas 96 percent of the candidates did not have any disability issues.

8. In your current workplace or a previous workplace in the retail industry within Gauteng, South Africa, have you been discriminated against on the grounds of your disability. Please pick appropriately

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Yes	0%	0	22
no	100%	22	22

Table 8: discrimination faced based on disability

Among the 22 candidates who participated in the survey, all 22 candidates claimed that they were not discriminated against on the grounds of physical disability. Though it is found that physical disability is one of the primary grounds on which discrimination takes place, no instances are being faced by such candidates.

9. Organizational service term (effect of employment equity on retention) average weekly working hours

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Less than 40	8%	2	24
40-50 hours	71%	17	24
51-60 hours	17%	4	24
More than 60 hours	4%	1	24

Table 9: Service term

8 percent of the candidates work for less than 40 hours a week. However, 71 percent of the candidates work for 40-50 hours, 17 percent of the candidates work for more than 51-60 hours, and 4 percent of the candidates work for more than 60 hours. The organization needs to ensure that the employees are working on time and not extending their times as it can lead them to suffer from demotivation and fatigue.

10. How long have you worked in your current workplace

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Less than 6 months	0%	0	24
6-12 months	13%	3	24
Less than 2 yeas	4%	1	24
2-5 years	17%	4	24
5-10 years	48%	11	24
More than 10 years	17%	4	24

Table 10: Service term

The table represents that 17 percent of the candidates have worked in their present workplace for more than 10 years, 48 percent of them have worked for 5-10 years, 17 percent of them have worked for 2-5 years, 4 percent have worked for less than 2 years, 13 percent of the candidates have worked for 6-12 months. The value of the standard deviation is 3.53. retention of the employees is one of the significant factors. The companies must conduct activities to retain them.

11. How long do you intend to remain in your current workplace

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Less than 3 years	8%	2	24
3-5 years	21%	5	24
6-10 years	4%	1	24
10 years+	4%	1	24
Until I retire	21%	5	24
Not sure	42%	10	24
Other (please specify period)	0%	0	24

Table 11: Intention rate to remain in the organization

8 percent of the candidates claim that they want to remain in the organization for less than 3 years, 21 percent of the candidates claim that they want to work for 3-5 years. 4 percent of the candidates wants to work for 6-10 years, 4 percent of the candidates want to work for 10 years and above, 21 percent of the candidates want to work in their organization until they retire. However, 42 percent of the candidates are not sure about it. The value of the standard deviation is 3.53. Organizations need to ensure that they are taking some initiatives to retain the employees.

12. If you were to leave your current organization, will the cause of your leaving be due to employment inequalities in the organization? Please tick as appropriate

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Strongly disagree	33%	8	24
Disagree	29%	7	24
Neutral	17%	4	24
Agree	13%	3	24
Strongly agree	08%	2	24

Table 12: employee inequality leading to the turnover of employees

8 percent of the candidates claim that they would leave the organization because of the prevalence of employee inequality. However, 33 percent of the candidates strongly disagree with it. The value of std is 2.32. therefore, the organization must change its practices of operations to prevent inequalities as it is one of the basic reasons for the turnover of employees.

13. State of retention- how likely are you to work within your organization in the next year? Please tick appropriately

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Very unlikely	4%	1	24
Unlikely	0%	0	24
Neutral	13%	3	24
Likely	29%	7	24
Very likely	54%	13	24

54 percent of the candidates claim that they are very likely to work for their organization, whereas 4 percent of the candidates are unlikely to work in the organization. the value of the standard deviation here is 4.75. organizations need to conduct practices to retain the employees as employee retention is very important.

14. How well do you understand your career advancement and promotion in your current organisation? Please tick appropriately.

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Not well understood	13%	3	24
Somehow	8%	2	24
Neutral	8%	2	24
Well	33%	8	24
Very well	38%	9	24

Training and career development are very important in employee behaviour. It helps in motivating them. among the 24 candidates who took part in the survey. 38 percent of the candidates are very much aware of the career advancements and promotions whereas 13 percent of the candidates are not aware of it. The value of the standard deviation is 3.06. Organizations need to offer training and career advancement to the employees to motivate them and retain them.

15. How pleased are you with how you are treated in the workplace? Please tick appropriately

Options	Response rate	No of respondents	Total no of respondents
Not pleased	8%	2	24
Somehow pleased	8%	2	24
Neutral	17%	4	24
Pleased	46%	11	24
Very pleased	21%	5	24

From the above data, it is clear that 8 percent of the candidates are not pleased with the treatment which they get from the organization, 17 percent of the candidates were neutral in their opinion whereas 21 percent of the candidates were very pleased. The value of the standard deviation is 3.31. the organization needs to change its policies towards the employees to make them feel pleased. This can help them in their employee retention.

16. Career-please tick appropriately

Options	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Standard deviation
There are salary gaps within the same employee class in my workplace	13% (3)	4% (1)	26 % (6)	35% (8)	22 % (5)	2.42
Salary increase follows an affair process	17% (4)	30% (7)	30 % (7)	9% (2)	13 % (3)	2.06
Promotion criteria are clear and fair	4% (1)	33 % (8)	33 % (8)	25% (6)	4% (1)	3.19
There are equal opportunities for training	4 % (1)	25% (6)	25% (6)	38% (9)	8% (2)	2.93

Table 13: discriminations in terms of opportunities

From the table, it is being comprehended that 22 percent of the candidates strongly agree to the fact that there is a gap in the salary among the same employees. The value of std is 2.42 which indicates that the management must look into the matter and conduct a fair pay system.

13 percent of the candidates strongly agree that the increase in the salary is not conducted fairly. The value of the std is 2.06. the organization needs to ensure a fair increase in the salary.

4 percent of the candidates strongly disagree that the promotion is strongly fair and 33 percent of the candidates disagree with it. The value of the std is 3.19 and hence, the criteria of the promotion must be altered by the organizations.

38 percent of the candidates agree that there are equal opportunities whereas 6 percent of candidates claim to disagree with it. The value of the standard deviation is 2.93. the organization must ensure that equal opportunities are conducted.

17. What do you think makes it difficult to achieve equity in employment in your workplace or based on a previous workplace in the retail industry?

The following feedback was provided in the survey which the participants indicate the reason that there were barriers to achieving employment equity namely: lack of suitably qualified candidates, discrimination is often misinterpreted due to race and gender. Then some participants indicated education level. Some say a lack of sufficient staff. Most participants say either policies or assigned senior managers not fully driving employment equity-related matters, lack of succession planning, high staff turnover, job grading, remuneration not benchmarked

Chapter 4.3. Presentation and discussion of the qualitative data (interview)

Question 1: What do you think makes it difficult to achieve equity in employment in your workplace or based on previous work in the retail industry

From the interviews which are being conducted, a various number of reasons are taken into the consideration. Discrimination based on race; gender is some of the significant reasons. Longer hours of working, bad organizational management are some of the factors identified as well.

Chapter 4.4 Findings and discussion from the secondary research

According to MALGAS et al. (2019), in recent years it has been identified that in the retail chain of South Africa casualization of labor is conducted which is affecting the employee equity by quite a huge margin. Under the overall sales of the wholesalers has increased but the working condition of the employees that are associated with the retail sector of South Africa has gone down by quite a huge margin which has resulted in a decrease of

motivation among the employees and there is a huge number of employee turnover rate in this particular sector. The overall quality of the job associated with the employee has deteriorated by the employment process that is currently being conducted in the wholesale as well as the retail sector of South Africa. There is a direct relationship with casual labor along with the trading cycle of the retail outlets that are present in the country. A lot of casual Labour is being implemented by the company which is directly affecting the permanent members that are associated with it and it is also streamlining the decision-making process of the retail sector of South Africa. From this context, it can clearly be stated that the oral skills of the employees are not being enhanced and employees are looking forward to staying with a company for a short period and then they are going to move forward to another company in the retail sector in which their payment is more. There is an optimum reason for high job insecurity among the temporary workers that are being hired by the retail sector of South Africa which is decreasing the flexibility of the job and workload is steadily increasing for the associated employees of the retail sector in South Africa. With the presence of optimum job pressure the stress level of the employees is also Getting higher and most of the employees are then looking to adapt themselves to another temporary job in any other sector in South Africa.

It has been stated by Roman and Mason (2015), the employment equity in the retail sector of South Africa is not being maintained in a proper way which is directly affecting the oral profitability and major objective of the retail sector. Employment growth is not being implemented by the retail sector effectively which is affecting the well-being of the employees that are associated with the retail sector. There is a growth in the employment disparities with the implementation of unfavorable working conditions for the employees that are associated with the retail sector. Great difficulties are being faced by the companies that are present in the retail sector of South Africa in transforming itself towards the various financial implication that is being faced by the employees that are associated with the retail sector. immaturity of the people, as well as institutions that are currently associated with a retail sector, are not considered the various aspects that are essential for the implementation of proper employee engagement. The nature, as well as philosophy that is associated with employment equity, is not being conducted effectively and implementation of the different legal framework is also not impacting the employee

engagement in the retail sector of South Africa positively. It must also be stated that most of the response that has been generated from the employees that are associated with the retail sector of South Africa is negative which clearly identifies the fact that the employees are not being provided with proper write that is associated with them and the business that is being conducted by the retail sector of Africa is not being conducted in an ethical way which is adding up towards the employee turnover rate by quite a huge margin.

In the words of Malgas, Khatle, and Mason (2017), the women that are associated with the employee percentage in the retail sector of South Africa is not very high and women are looked down upon as low skilled employees and they are very much less likely to be adopted or employed by the retail sector of South Africa. This clearly states the fact that diversification is not one of the major competencies that are associated with the retail sector of South Africa. Due to this context and give the absence of diversity in the workplace culture many top talents in the market often do not want to be a part of the industry and the retail sector is not properly aware of this fact in South Africa. The management of the companies that are associated with the retail sector of South Africa look down upon women as an inferior part of the society and they also believe that in the rural areas the women are not capable of conducting work in the retail sector effectively. But it must also be stated that it is an optimum duty of an employer to ensure the fact that there is the presence of optimum employee diversity in the workplace so that there is present or a proper culture in the workplace which is very much beneficial for the overall development of the organizational culture. The employee bias that is present in the retail sector of South Africa needs to be eradicated to ensure the fact that women are provided with the same opportunity in the retail sector of South Africa as compared to that of men. South African retail sector plays a very crucial role in the overall profitability of the country but from the perspective of operational enhancement, the sector is not capable of generating employee equity properly and effectively. The overall progress that has been conducted by the retail sector of South Africa in the promotion of gender equality, as well as empowerment of women, is not conducted properly and effectively and a proper focus has not been implemented on the development of entrepreneurship of women in South Africa.

According to Roman and Mason (2015), the overall institutional transformation that has been conducted in the retail sector of South Africa over the years is not conducted positively and a lot of employment disparities have been identified in this particular sector of South Africa. Although the employment equity act is capable of identifying the various discriminatory laws that need to be adopted in the country however they are not feasible enough in ensuring a proper competitive advantage in the market. All the retail sector of South Africa has been beneficial enough and generating a lot of revenue over the years however the various policies that have been implemented by the country are not practical enough to create proper employment equity in the workplace and this has directly affected the workplace condition of the employees that are associated with the country. The retail sector of South Africa hosts a wide number of employees and properly implemented strategies must be initiated to identify the future feasibility of the workforce in the sector. By looking at the various aspect of workplace conditions it can be identified that the Human Resource Department of the various companies that are associated with the retail sector of South Africa is not capable of generating proper responses to meet the various transformation challenges in the country. The overall lack of necessary skills that are associated with the employees in this sector can be identified as the absence of employment equity factor in the retail sector of the country. The hiring, as well as development of the staff in the retail sector, is not conducted properly and effectively which directly contributes towards the turnover rate in the retail sector of South Africa.

It has been stated by Warden, Han, and Nzawou (2018), the micro-retail business in South Africa is facing a lot of employee turnover rates due to the absence of optimum employment equity in this particular sector. The retail sector of South Africa is not capable to implement various developed models as well as Framework by the help of age it is possible to increase the job satisfaction as well as organisational commitment of the employees which directly affects the turnover rate of the employees by quite a huge margin. Looking at the present perfect of the business and the current condition of the retail sector of South Africa it can clearly be stated that the various internal factors that are controlled by the associated employees of the retail sector are not conducted properly and effectively which not only creates a lack of communication in the workplace, but it also does not help the retail business to focus on expectations of the employees in the

workplace properly. A proper Holistic view on this aspect clearly States the effect that optimum training is not provided to the Employees and the working condition of the employees are also not positive in nature. The management practices that are followed by the retail sector of South Africa are also not optimum enough in providing proper motivation to the Employees associated with the sector and ultimately lead to Staff turnover.

Chapter 5. Conclusion and recommendations:

To conclude it can be stated that the overall development that has been generated in the employment equity as well as employee retention aspect in South Africa is not quite smooth and various changes need to be implemented to provide employment equity and Employment retention effectively. Although there are a lot of Legislative aspects that have been initiated in the country to ensure defect that proper employment equity is provided in different fields however the companies that working in the country has not been capable of properly implementing employment equity in the world plus effectively. There is a lack of Trust among the associated employees in the companies and job satisfaction is not very high under this context. The employment equity act was generated by looking at the present perspective of the business and the establishment of the employment equity was generated by quite a huge margin after the pass of the act. It must also be stated that the companies that are present in the South Africa retail sector of Gauteng need to follow the policies that have been designed by the government in order to ensure the fact that policies regarding employment equity are implemented properly and effectively and staff retention of the employees are also increased and improved drastically. Companies need to ensure the fact that employment equity must be conducted properly and effectively to improve the motivation level of the employees and also provide equal opportunities to each and every individual that is associated with the retail industry in South Africa. With the presence of optimum employment equity, it will be possible for the companies to retain employees effectively and the employee turnover rate will go down by quite a huge margin which is a very positive aspect in the employment sector. Every employee that is associated with the Retail Industry must be provided equal opportunities and they must be treated in an optimum way as the employees in a Retail Industry are the front runner of the business. To maintain proper customer satisfaction as fate and in order to ensure that a proper relationship is maintained with the customers, the employment equity policies must be generated effectively. With the presence of optimum employment equity, it will be possible for the company to identify the various policies that need to be initiated to make the employees understand the importance of customer satisfaction and this will also help in retaining the employees that are associated with this particular sector.

The literature review sheds a proper light on the various aspect of employee equity policies that have been implemented in the retail sector in South Africa. The man that is associated with the retail companies that are present in South Africa is to sustain in the competitive market and improve the position of the companies in the market by the utilization of the resources that are associated with it to gain a competitive edge. However, while conducting this process the companies that are associated in the Retail Industry sell in maintaining employment equity which ultimately leads to employee turnover by quite a huge margin. In other words, the retention rate of the companies that are associated with the Retail Industry of South Africa is very low which is going to affect the overall capability of the companies that are present in the market. In order to attract the attention of the top talent that is present in the market, retail companies need to initiate employment equity so that the companies can give a competitive advantage over the competitors and also maintain a proper relationship with their associated customers. There is a presence of optimum dissatisfaction among the employees that is present in the Retail Industry of South Africa due to the presence of different factors including the significance of favoritism of certain employees over others and there is also the presence of unfair discrimination. Various other factors such as the absence of job security are also responsible for deteriorating the relationship that exists between the management of a retail company and the employees that are associated with it. Labor exploitation has also been conducted in various sectors in the Retail Industry which has resulted in employee turnover rate by quite a huge margin and optimum pressure that is provided on the employees creates a huge amount of stress on them.

It is the optimum duty of an employer in the Retail Industry to ensure that the health and wellbeing of an employee are maintained properly but in the retail sector of South Africa, it has been identified that this aspect is not conducted in a proper way which has ultimately led to the fact that labor exploitation is conducted by quite a huge margin which has not helped the company to implement employment equity effectively. Many employees that are associated with the retail sector of South Africa are not paid properly which has affected their motivation level and it also goes against the ethical aspects that need to be followed in a particular business. With the absence of a legitimate salary, many employees that are associated in the retail sector of leaving their job and look for another

company that provides a better salary in this context. It must also be stated that comfortable workplace condition is also not provided to the Employees which directly affects their motivation level and the employees do not look forward to implementing a various process by the help of which they can improve their motivation level by quite a huge margin. The efficiency of the employees remains the same over the years since the company does not look forward and the various process that can be implemented to make the employees much more productive than before. There is optimum discrimination among the lower-level employees in the retail sector and the higher-level employees which helps in creating a barrier in communication among the different tiers of the company. All this aspect combines and creates a high level of employee turnover in the retail sector which is a huge problem for the industry and with the implementation of important steps it might be possible to improve the current condition of the employees in the Retail Industry of South Africa. Leadership plays a very crucial role in the development of employment equity, and it is also capable of improving the employee retention rate of companies by quite a huge margin. The leaders that are associated with a company helps in bringing the change that is essential for the development of a company and leaders are also capable of changing the attitude and behaviors of an employee towards the workplace. The influence that is generated by a leader on the employees that are working in the workplace is an important factor that needs to be taken into account while understanding the various aspects of employee retention. Looking at the present perspective of the business that is being conducted in the retail sector of South Africa it can clearly be stated that the leadership strategies that are being followed by the leaders in the Retail Industry are not optimum enough in maintaining employment equity and it also fails in achieving the employment retention rate that is expected from the industry. It is very much important to state that the employees of a company are the ones that are capable of initiating the various strategies that need to be implemented to make a company competitive in the market and also generate larger revenue in return. However, if the employees of a company are not happy in the workplace and discrimination is conducted in the workplace then it is not possible for a company to make the employees motivated enough to work towards a better future for the company. This is the same case with the retail sector of South Africa and the lack of job satisfaction among the employees

plays a very important role in the decrease of employee retention rate of the employees. It is a very important aspect that needs to be taken into account by the retail sector and proper steps and policies must be initiated by the help of which it will be possible to develop the skills of the employees and maintain a proper relationship with them in order to generate better profitability in the future scenario of the market. Proper career aspects must be provided to the employees that are associated with a retail sector in order to ensure defect that the career development of the employees is generated progressively, and the employees are happy in the workplace and look forward to meeting the Expectations of the company in a proper and effective way. Organizational culture, uncertainty avoidance index, long term versus short term orientation, and power distance index play a very crucial role in the implementation of employment equity and initiation of better employee retention rate in the retail sector of South Africa.

In order to cope up with the current problems that are being faced by the retail industry of South Africa, the following steps can be initiated which will be very much helpful in understanding the process that must be followed to implement employment equity and generate a better employee retention rate -

Recommendation 1. Implementation of optimum communication in the workplace in it to be initiated in order to ensure the fact that all the employees that are associated with the company are aware of the responsibilities towards the company. With the flow of proper communication, it will also be possible for the employees to state the various problems that are being faced by them in the workplace to the higher authority. The higher authority of the company must initiate the proper steps with the help of which it will be possible to meet the expectations of the employees and also solve their problems effectively (Kekana 2019). The proper communication process will also be helpful for the leaders that are associated with the Retail Industry of South Africa in understanding the problems that are being faced by the company and initiate various steps with the help of which it will be possible to improve the motivation level of the employees by quite a huge margin.

Recommendation 2. Proper research must be conducted by the retail sector to understand the core problems that are being faced by the employees. By the utilization of online or offline surveys, it will be possible for the retail sector to understand the main

problems that are being faced by the employees at are working in the retail sector to find out an optimum solution towards the development of the working condition of the employees (Abu-Laban and Gabriel 2020). With the help of our research, the problems that are being faced by the employees can easily be identified by the management of the retail sector and the optimum solution will be generated which will improve the employee retention rate by quite a huge margin.

Recommendation 3. The decision-making process that is going to be undertaken by the retail companies that are present in the retail sector of South Africa must be conducted by taking into account the ideas that are associated with the employees in the company. If the employees feel like their voice is being taken into account, they will feel like they are an important part of the company which will not only improve the employee retention rate but will also improve the motivation level of the employees by quite a huge margin (Saar 2018). Each and every statement that is going to be delivered by the employees for undertaking decision-making process must be taken into account by the company properly and effectively so that it can find out the optimum solution to different problems as employees are quite aware of the current trends in the market and they know the various perspective of the employees which will be beneficial for the company in increasing their profitability as well as improve their market share by quite a huge margin.

Recommendation 4. The target that is going to be associated by the company must be transparent to the employees that are associated with the retail sector. Proper accountability must be shown to the Employees regarding the target that has been selected by the company and the various reason behind selecting the target must also be explained to the employees so that they are also on board with the future mission and vision that has been identified for the company (Rioux, Patton and Agocs 2018). The leaders of the retail sector will play a very crucial role in this contest as they will be capable of effectively communicating the future goals that have been selected by the company and how much the company, as well as the employees, are going to be beneficial from this aspect.

Recommendation 5. A proper policy must be maintained by the company for the hiring practices has discrimination in hiring must not be conducted which will affect the

implementation of employment equity. Hiring must be conducted by looking at the current performance of the employee and their positive mindset. To implement innovation in the system it is very much important for companies to understand that the top talent in the market must be hired in the management to identify the new trend that is available in the market effectively and also ensure the fact that the company is capable of adapting itself with the various changes in the market (Anand 2018).

Recommendation 6. Regular feedback must be taken by the management of the companies that are operating in the retail sector of South Africa to understand the working condition of the employees and also understand if the new policies that are going to be implemented in the workplace have affected the workplace condition positively. Regular feedback will also ensure the fact that the communication flow in the workplace is going to be maintained properly (Henry et al. 2017).

Recommendation 7. Each and every employee that is currently associated with the retail sector of South Africa must be treated in an equal way so that there is the absence of any kind of discrimination in the workplace. Avoiding discrimination is going to create an optimum culture in the workplace which is going to be highly beneficial for the implementation of employment equity and it will also improve the employee retention rate by quite a huge margin.

Recommendation 8. The onboarding program that is going to be initiated by the retail companies must be in accordance with its present culture. Extension of the onboarding program can be initiated if an employee is not properly accustomed to the culture and feel like they are still not ready to be a part of the company (Agocs and Burr 2016).

Recommendation 9. Optimum training can be provided to the leaders that are associated with the company in order to ensure that they are aware of the steps that must be taken to improve the workplace condition of the employees properly. The leaders will also be trained to initiate optimum communication in the workplace.

Chapter 6. Timing milestones:

1	Stage 1: Area of interest identified	15/10/2020	Completed
2	Stage 2: Specific topic selected	27/10/2020	Completed
3	Stage 3: Topic refined to develop a dissertation proposal	10/01/2021	Completed
4	Stage 4: Proposal written and submitted	29/01/2021	Completed
5	Stage 5: Collection of data and information	30/04/2021	Complete data collection by 30/04/2021
6	Stage 6: Analysis and interpretation of collected data/information	30/05/2021	Complete data collection by 30/04/2021

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Annexures – Survey results

Title of Study Impact of Employment Equity Policies on staff retention. The case of retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa Version Number and Date Version 1 – 30 January 2021

You are being invited to participate in a research study. Before you decide whether to participate, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and feel free to ask us if you would like more information or if there is anything that you do not understand. Please also feel free to discuss this with your friends, relatives, and work colleagues. We would like to stress that you do not have to accept this invitation and should only agree to take part if you want to.

Thank you for reading this.

What is the purpose of the study?

This research is aimed at what the effects of employment equity policies in South Africa have on staff retention. The objective of this study is to explore:

- Employment equity

- The barriers to achieve equity in the employment policy.

- Retention of staff in companies

- Effect of employment equity on the retention of staff in the companies.

The findings from the study will be used to allow better insight into experiences of work in the field. The research aim of this paper is to analyse an effect of employment equity on retention of staff in companies in the South Africa. The goal is offering description of different complex issues, contextual factors, multiple orientations, and forces impose upon employment equity implementation and retention of staff through the vehicle of investigation of South African companies.

Why have I been chosen to take part?

All HRM staff, who are involved in either developing policies, recruiting staff and assist in staff development are being invited to participate. Hopefully, between 20 and 25 will choose to take part altogether.

Do I have to take part?

No. Your participation is entirely voluntary. You can choose whether to take part. Even if you choose to take part, you can change your mind and you are free to withdraw at any time without giving any explanation. There will be no negative impact or disadvantage to you if you choose not to take part, nor if you change your mind and choose to withdraw.

What will happen if I take part?

As a participant you will be asked to complete online questionnaires. The person that will be communicating with you is Pieter van Ellewee, the primary consultant in collaboration and the University of Liverpool. All communication will take place at a time that suits you and the consultant and will be planned and scheduled ahead of time. Questionnaires will include mostly closed-ended questions with some open-ended questions and should typically not take more than 30 minutes to complete. You may be asked to participate in follow up questionnaires or conversations if needed at your convenience. Questionnaire data will be stored on a secure server and the stored data will be used in the study.

How will my data be used?

The University processes personal data as part of its research and teaching activities in

accordance with the lawful basis of 'public task', and in accordance with the University's

purpose of "advancing education, learning and research for the public benefit". Under UK data protection legislation, the University acts as the Data Controller for personal data collected as part of the University's research. The Dissertation

Advisor acts as the Data Processor for this study, and any queries relating to the handling of your personal data can be sent

to Dr. Veeresh Srivastava, V.Srivastava@liverpool.ac.uk. Further information on how your data will be used can be found in the table below.

How will my data be collected?	Using online questionnaires.
How will my data be stored?	Electronically on an encrypted hard drive and my university OneDrive
How long will my data be stored for?	Data will be anonymised and stored for a period of three years according to the data policy of the organisation
What measures are in place to protect the security and confidentiality of my data?	The computer and file server where data will be stored requires authentication to access. encrypted data. All data will be anonymised to further protect the identity of participants
Will my data be anonymised?	Yes, continually as data is collected.
How will my data be used?	All data will be anonymised and will be used to inform this dissertation consultation project.
Who will have access to my data?	the Consultancy Project Advisor (University of Liverpool) and the student investigator
Will my data be archived for use in other research projects in the future?	No
How will my data be destroyed?	Once data has been used and stored for the required period of time it will be deleted from all drives.

It will be necessary to send data into the EU for the dissertation to be marked and moderated by the University of Liverpool and Laureate Education. To protect the identity of participants, data will only be sent once it has been anonymised and submitted securely in the classroom portal of the University.

Expenses and / or payments

No expenses or any other payments will be made to participants for the purpose of this study.

Are there any risks in taking part?

There should be no risk in taking part for any participant. If participants experience any discomfort or disadvantage while participating in the project, they can inform the student investigator (Pieter van Ellewee, P.Van-Ellewee@liverpool.ac.uk) at any time.

Are there any benefits in taking part?

There is no benefit, monetary or otherwise to participants other than positively adding to the subject of the affects employment equity policies have on staff retention.

What will happen to the results of the study?

The consultation project will produce actionable objectives in a business report as well as an academic consultation report submitted to the University of Liverpool as part of the ongoing qualification of the student investigator. The study results will be made available the University of Liverpool for grading and participants will not be identifiable in the results.

What will happen if I want to stop taking part?

Participants can withdraw their participation in the study at any time, without explanation. Results up to the period of withdrawal may be used, with consent from the participant. Otherwise, the participant may request that the results collected on them be destroyed and no further use is made of them. It is important to note that any such results can only be withdrawn prior to anonymisation. If a participant would like to withdraw from the study, they can contact the student investigator, Pieter van Ellewee at **P.Van-Ellewee@liverpool.ac.uk** at any time.

What if I am unhappy or if there is a problem?

If you are unhappy, or if there is a problem, please feel free to let us know by contacting Dr. Veeresh Srivastava, **V.Srivastava@liverpool.ac.uk** and we will try to help. If you remain unhappy or have a complaint which you feel you cannot come to us with then you should contact the University's Research Ethics and Integrity Office at ethics@liv.ac.uk. When contacting the Research Ethics and Integrity Office, please provide details of the name or description of the study (so that it can be identified), the researcher(s) involved, and the details of the complaint you wish to make. The University strives to maintain the highest standards of rigour in the processing of your data. However, if you have any concerns about the way in which the University processes your personal data, it is important that you are aware of your right to lodge a complaint with the Information Commissioner's Office by calling (+44) 0303 123 1113

Who can I contact if I have further questions?

For further questions, participants can contact:

- The Dissertation Advisor, Veeresh Srivastava, **V.Srivastava@liverpool.ac.uk**
- The student investigator, Pieter van Ellewee at **P.Van-Ellewee@liverpool.ac.uk**

Participant consent form

Version number & date: Version 1 – 30 January 2021

Title of the research project: **Impact of Employment Equity Policies on staff retention. The case of retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa**

Name of researcher(s): Pieter van Ellewee

1 I confirm that I have read and have understood the information sheet dated 30 January 2021 for the above study, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily

12
Standard Deviation

24
Responses

2 I understand that taking part in the study involves online questionnaires and that findings will be recorded in text form and anonymised

11
Standard Deviation

22
Responses

3 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to stop taking part and can withdraw from the study at any time without giving any reason and without my rights being affected. In addition, I understand that I am free to decline to answer any particular question or questions

100% (20)
YES

0% (0)
NO

10
Standard Deviation

20
Responses

4 I understand that I can ask for access to the information I provide, and I can request the destruction of that information if I wish at any time prior to August 2021. I understand that following August 2021, I will no longer be able to request access to or withdrawal of the information I provide

100% (22)
YES

0% (0)
NO

11
Standard Deviation

22
Responses

5 I understand that the information I provide will be held securely and in line with data protection requirements at the University of Liverpool until it fully anonymised after which it will be stored on the secured organisational file server for sharing and use by other authorised researchers to support another research in the future

6 I understand that signed consent forms and original audio/video recordings/questionnaires will be retained on the secured organisation file server accessible to the researcher and top management for a period of 3 years after the research is completed. I agree for my personal data to be transferred into the EU and I have been informed of the safeguards in place to protect my personal data when it is transferred.

7 I agree to take part in the above study

8 Date

2021-07-27 00:00

2021-07-26 00:00

2021-07-26 00:00

2021-07-26 00:00

2021-07-26 12:00

2021-07-25 00:00

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2021-07-21 00:00

2021-07-21 12:00

2021-07-21 00:00

Participant name

DANIELLA ZAMBELLI

JOHANNESBURG

ZA

daniellaz1979@gmail.com

Sean Coleman

Springs

ZA

sean@tffm.co.za

Krisjan Fourie

Johannesburg

ZA

krisjanfourie@gmail.com

Nadette Voogd

Johannesburg

GB

nadettevoogd@icloud.com

Shaun Gregory Govender

Gauteng, South Africa

ZA

sgg@onetouchmobility.co.za

Philo

Johannesburg

ZA

Impact of Employment Equity Policies on staff retention. The case of retail industry in Gauteng, South Africa

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHICS

9 What is your gender?

Bchihungwa05@yahoo.com

Dave Crothall

Hartebeespoort Dam

ZA

Dave.crothall@gmail.com

Sharmaine

King-williams-town

ZA

prince.sharmaine@gmail.com

Mark

Roodepoort Gauteng

ZA

Markniialash@gmail.com

Rian

Roodepoort

ZA

rianfish@gmail.com

Thokozane Ngwenya

Johannesburg

ZA

Thokozane.ngwenya3@gmail.com

Chantel Ruppig

Alberton

ZA

chantelesterhuyse6@gmail.com

Anton de Beer

Johannesburg

US

anton@rampar.co.za

SH Day

Johannesburg

ZA

stephanday@gmail.com

Charissa Arumugam

Gauteng

GB

charissaa@multifranchise.co.za

Natasha Jacobs

Krugersdorp, Gauteng

ZA

nengelbrecht7@gmail.com

Bhavika Singh

Boksburg

ZA

bsingh@motusnissan.co.za

Henry Barnard

Boksburg, JHB, Gauteng

ZA

hbarnard@motusnissan.co.za

Debbie Smith

Gauteng South Africa

ZA

dsmith@motusnissan.co.za

Hennie Pieterse

Centuiron

ZA

hpieterse@motusnissan.co.za

Adri Delport

Johannesburg

ZA

adrivz@multifranchise.co.za

Zinhle Duma

Johannesburg

GB

zinhled@motuscorp.co.za

Maryka De Faria

Pretoria

ZA

marykej@multifranchise.co.za

LTK Day

Johannesburg

ZA

tryzton22@hotmail.com

GB

10 What is your age?

0% (0)
Under 25 years

13% (3)
25 – 30 years

33% (8)
31 – 40 years

50% (12)
41 – 50 years

4% (1)
Above 50 years

4.53
Standard Deviation

24
Responses

11 Please indicate your relevant/related highest education attainment levels to date. Please tick the most appropriate below

4% (1)
Below Standard 8 (Grade 10) or equivalent

0% (0)
Standard 9(Grade 11) or equivalent

25% (6)
Standard 10 (Matric or Grade 12) or equivalent

8% (2)
Post Matric

29% (7)
Diploma

13% (3)
Undergraduate Degree - Batchelors Degree

13% (3)
Post Graduate Degree - Honours Degree

4% (1)
Post Graduate Degree - Masters

0% (0)
Post Graduate Degree - Doctorate

4% (1)
Other (Please Specify)

2.29
Standard Deviation

24
Responses

Advanced Diploma (NQ7)

12 What is your current employment status

0% (0)
Unemployed

83% (19)
Employed - Full Time

9% (2)
Employed - Part Time

9% (2)
Employed - Contract Worker

0% (0)
Employed - Temporary

0% (0)
Other (Please Specify)

6.84
Standard Deviation

23
Responses

14 In your current workplace or a previous workplace in retail industry within Gauteng, South Africa, have you been discriminated on the grounds of your race. Please tick appropriately.
Have been discriminated for being:

14% (3)
African

5% (1)
Indian

0% (0)
Coloured

76% (16)
Caucasian

14% (3)
Other (Please Specify)

23
Responses

White

None

BBBEE

15 Disability discrimination Do you have any physical disability?

4% (1)
Yes

96% (23)
No

11
Standard Deviation

24
Responses

16 In your current workplace or a previous workplace in retail industry within Gauteng, South Africa, have you been discriminated on the grounds of your disability. Please tick appropriately

0% (0)
Yes

100% (22)
No

11
Standard Deviation

22
Responses

17 SECTION C: ORGANIZATION SERVICE TERM (Effect of Employment equity on staff retention) Average weekly working hours

8% (2)
Less than 40

71% (17)
40 – 50 hours

17% (4)
51-60 hours

4% (1)
more than 60 hours

6.44
Standard Deviation

24
Responses

18 How long have you worked in the current workplace?

0% (0)

Less than 6 months

13% (3)

6 - 12 months

4% (1)

less than 2 years

17% (4)

2 - 5 years

48% (11)

5-10 years

17% (4)

More than 10 years

3.53

Standard Deviation

23

Responses

19 How long do you intend to remain in your current workplace?

8% (2) less than 3 years	21% (5) 3 – 5 years	4% (1) 6 - 10 years	4% (1) 10 years +
21% (5) until I retire	42% (10) Not sure	0% (0) Other (please specify period).....	
3.25 Standard Deviation	24 Responses		

20 If you were to leave your current organization, will the cause of your leaving be due to employment inequalities in the organization. Please tick as appropriate.

If you were to leave your current organization, will the cause of your leaving be due to employment inequalities in the organization. Please tick a

21 State of retention - How likely are you to work with your organization in the next one year? Please tick appropriately

How likely are you to work with your organization in the next one year? Please tick appropriately

22 How well do you understand your career advancement and promotion in your current organization? Please tick appropriately

How well do you understand your career advancement and promotion in your current organization?

23 How pleased are you with how you are treated in the workplace? Please tick appropriately

How pleased are you with how you are treated in the workplace? Please tick appropriately

25 SECTION E: BARRIERS TO ACHIEVEMENT OF EQUITY IN EMPLOYMENT POLICY
What do you think makes it difficult to achieve equity in employment in your work place or based on a previous workplace in the retail industry?

LACK OF SUITABLY QUALIFIED CANDIDATES; RETAIL INDUSTRY REMUNERATION STRUCTURE DOESN'T ENTICE EE CANDIDATES; RETAIL INDUSTRY INVOLVES LONG WORKING HOURS AND THIS DOESN'T ENTICE EE GRADUATES; DEMAND FOR SUITABLY TRAINED EE CANDIDATES MEANS THEY ARE VERY MOBILE AND AN EMPLOYER WILL BATTLE TO RETAIN THEM

Discrimination is often misinterpreted due to race and gender, generally it comes down to whether an employee can or cannot get the job done....

Race, language and sexual orientation

Affirmative Action

Lack of high skilled employees

Education levels

Not sufficient staff

Not applicable

N/a

I honestly don't think this is a issue that will ever get resolved

Nothing

When an employment opportunity is denied

Our South African laws with regards to EE

I have not personally had this experienced but there are some individuals that feel due to their skin color or gender, they can not be promoted

This is difficult for me to comment as I have been with the company for 30 years, I have personally never felt that I have been discriminated against, but have been in Equity discussions where others have felt the discrimination. This is not only against African but all races that feel that they are discriminated against due to achieving Equity. It is extremely difficult to have everyone happy with choices that are made. I feel that Motus do their utmost best to train their staff to understand the reasoning of Equity and what it is about, it is a personal choice on whether you accept this or not. Being in a management position the understanding is more clear than your employees.

BEE policies create barriers as some more qualified candidates are overlooked due to the BEE candidates getting preference.

BEE.....it is a Disgrace in SA

Assigned senior managers not fully driving EE related matters, lack of succession planning, high staff turnover, job grading, remuneration not benchmarked, etc.

We have to achieve the BEE level within our workplace and that means you have to employ staff that are not educated to do the work function to the fullest